

#24 2025

Xi Jinping's Southeast Asian Tour

By Glauco Winkel

Policy Brief

What are the objectives of Xi Jinping's Southeast Asian tour? Following the intensification of US tariffs on Asian products, promoted by Donald Trump's administration, the Chinese President made a series of strategic visits to Vietnam, Malaysia and Cambodia over the last week (Fortune, 2025). The initiative seeks to strengthen regional ties at a time of growing Sino-American rivalry, marked by the dispute for international prominence, trade tensions and the need for Beijing to position itself as a reliable partner. The results of the trip include the strengthening of China's presence in Southeast Asia, the signing of bilateral agreements and investments in strategic sectors, as well as the proposal of an alternative regional security model to challenge the predominance of the United States.

With the United States increasing its tariffs on other Asian nations, China is finding room to deepen its regional ties. This move is in line with Xi Jinping's strategy of strengthening relations with Asian countries in an attempt to build a coordinated front against Washington's unilateral actions (The Diplomat, 2025a). However, the countries of Southeast Asia have historically maintained a foreign policy based on non-alignment and the search for strategic autonomy, which could represent an obstacle to Beijing's plans. Faced with this, Xi will have two central challenges: to demonstrate that the Chinese objective is primarily economic cooperation and to mediate any sensitive territorial disputes, such as the claims in the South China Sea.

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The Chinese president's first international trip in 2025 to Southeast Asia reinforces the country's diplomatic offensive through bilateral agreements and strategic investments, in a context of uncertainty generated by the tariffs imposed by the Trump administration. In Vietnam, 40 agreements were signed, including an \$8 billion railway project connecting the Sino-Vietnamese border to the port of Hai Phong. In Malaysia, the visit focused on deepening trade ties as an alternative to the US market, although there are concerns that the nation will become a conduit for Chinese surpluses barred by the US, which could intensify competition with local industry. In Cambodia, Xi Jinping sought to consolidate the strategic partnership with investments in infrastructure, such as the Funan Techo Canal, a mega-project financed by China that would connect the capital Phnom Penh to the Gulf of Thailand, boosting the country's economic development, facilitating the transportation of goods and strengthening the competitiveness of local trade (The Diplomat, 2025b).

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In addition, amid the advances in relations with neighboring countries, Beijing's initiative to propose a regional security model that would act as a counterpoint to the leadership of the United States stands out. In April 2025, China convened a rare Central Conference on Working with Neighboring Countries, bringing together the top echelon of the People's Republic of China (PRC). On that occasion, Xi advocated the strengthening of a "community with a shared future" with the countries of the region and proposed the construction of an "Asian security model" (The Diplomat, 2025a). Sharing borders with 14 countries and considering 29 as part of its strategic periphery, the PRC seeks to guarantee its economic and national security through regional partnerships. Although geopolitical issues persist with traditional US allies such as Japan and South Korea, the countries have been strengthening their economic ties, especially in the midst of the tariff confrontation with the US.

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Given the above, we can see that Xi Jinping's tour of Southeast Asia aims to expand China's regional influence, deepening ties with neighboring countries, strengthening trade relations through bilateral agreements and strategic investments, in the midst of the trade war with the US, as well as proposing a new logic of regional security as an alternative to the American presence. In this context of tariff confrontation, Brazil can position itself as an alternative to Southeast Asia in key markets, especially in agriculture and farming. Lula's recent visit to Vietnam resulted in the opening of the Vietnamese market to Brazilian meat, as well as reinforcing the ambition to make Vietnam an export hub for Brazilian meat for the entire region. The Brazilian business community must be attentive to these opportunities, as well as to Brazil's negotiations with the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN).

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References

Chulunbaatar, Sumiya. "Amid US Tariff War, China Convenes Rare Central Conference on Neighborhood Diplomacy". *The Diplomat*, April 15, 2025a. <https://thediplomat.com/2025/04/amid-us-tariff-war-china-convenes-rare-central-conference-on-neighborhood-diplomacy/>.

Lim, Lionel. "Chinese President Xi Jinping kick-starts his 3-nation Southeast Asia tour as Trump flip-flops on tariffs". *Fortune*, April 14, 2025. <https://fortune.com/asia/2025/04/14/china-xi-jinping-3-nation-southeast-asia-tour-trump-flip-flops-tariffs/>.

Strangio, Sebastian. "China's Xi Hails Ties With Indonesia Ahead of Southeast Asia Tour". *The Diplomat*, April 14, 2025b. <https://thediplomat.com/2025/04/chinas-xi-hails-ties-with-indonesia-ahead-of-southeast-asia-tour/>.

The Author

Researcher on China and Southeast Asia at the Laboratory of Geopolitics, International Relations and Anti-Systemic Movements (LabGRIMA) of the Federal University of Pelotas (UFPe).

Glauco Winkel

The Policy Briefs are produced in partnership with the International Institute for Geopolitics & Security (IIGS) in Utah (USA), the Center for Studies on Geopolitics and International Relations (CENEGRI) and the Laboratory of Geopolitics, International Relations and Anti-Systemic Movements (LabGRIMA). The IIGS and CENEGRI are independent think tanks and non-profit organizations dedicated to research in the areas of Geopolitics and International Relations. LabGRIMA belongs to UFPe.

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How to quote

WINKEL, Glauco. Xi Jinping's Southeast Asian Tour. Policy Brief, LabGRIMA/CENEGRI/IIGS, n. 24, p. 1-7, 2024.

Current number

Policy Brief: Xi Jinping's Southeast Asian Tour, #24, 2025. LabGRIMA/CENEGRI/IIGS.

Policy Brief (Boteim de Geopolítica),
ISSN 2357-9455

Contact: atendimento@cenegri.org.br

Photo Credit: Pexels

 [10.5281/zenodo.15271069](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15271069)

